

DETECTION OF SMALL DELAMINATIONS IN A CFRP PLATE BY VIBRATION-BASED STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

In the context of modern high performance composite materials, a constant source of concern is the effect of impact by foreign objects. Such impacts can reasonably be expected during the life of the structure and can result in internal damage that is often difficult to detect and can reduce drastically strength and stability of the structure.

Hence, it is our goal to monitor the “health” of a structure permanently by using global methods which are based on the observation of the vibration characteristics. Visual inspections or local methods like ultrasonic methods can be applied subsequently.

The idea to consider a structure as an intelligent system which is able to perform a self-diagnosis is very challenging. However, this requires that the structure is equipped with a sensor network and actuation devices and an “artificial brain” which processes all the measurement information and which is able to make a decision on the structures health conditions.

The damage will usually lead to local changes of stiffness and damping (and in some applications changes of mass) causing a shift of the dynamic characteristics like eigenfrequencies, damping and mode shapes. However, these changes can be very small in the case of a small delamination in composite materials. Thus the method must be very sensitive to the fault.

As an indicator that an abnormal change in the structure has occurred, we construct a residual vector that is based on a consistency check between the actual structural response and a Hankel-matrix constructed from the response data of the undamaged system. The basic mathematical framework was developed by Basseville, Abdelghani and Benveniste [1]. In the present paper, the method is modified and combined with a smart structure technique, where the system is excited with random noise by an integrated actuator and the system response is measured. To determine the eigenfrequencies, dampings and mode shapes a modified ERA method was used.

As an example, a CFRP plate with stringers is investigated. A piezo-ceramic actuator and 4 piezo-ceramic sensors were attached to the structure. The plate was excited by random white noise and the strain response was measured. After measuring the plate in the undamaged state, a delamination was introduced by a an impactor mass with a kinetic energy of about 5 Joule causing a small damage which was subsequently increased by further impacts. Although the changes of the modal data are very small, it can be seen that the method is very sensitive so that even the damage on the smallest level can be observed. Based on statistical considerations, the jump of the indicator value turns out to be significantly different from the indicator values of the undamaged system.

KEYWORDS: Smart Structure, CFRP, Delamination, Variations in Temperature, Structural Health Monitoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Technical as well as economic reasons play a major role when developing composite materials. They are used increasingly because of their low density, high strength and stiffness. However, the mechanical properties of composite materials may degrade severely in the presence of damage. With the design of these materials new kinds of damage emerge. Due to the multilayer construction of composite materials delaminations between plies may occur and appear as a debonding of adjoining plies. Delaminations may be introduced by foreign objects. While costly components as electronics and engines may be replaced or updated regularly the structure mostly remains the same, fully passive and just follows a load versus cycle relationship [2]. The goal is to design an intelligent structural system that is able to perform a self-diagnosis from changes of the dynamic behaviour. The challenge here is that the delamination is very small so the damage must be detected in a very early stage. Thus the diagnostic method must be very sensitive to the fault.

An often discussed topic is the robustness of the damage indicator towards variations in environmental conditions such as temperature. Experimental as well as theoretical investigations were made to increase this robustness. Figure 1 shows the principle experimental setup of the Smart Structure Concept.

Fig.1: Smart Structure Concept

The structure is excited by means of a piezo-ceramic actuator, which is driven by a voltage with approximately zero mean Gaussian white noise characteristics. Accelerometers, strain gages, fiber optic sensors etc. can measure the dynamic response. In this case piezo-ceramic sensors were used. The eigenfrequencies, damping coefficients and mode shapes were determined using the Stochastic Subspace Identification method. As examples two different CFRP plates with and without stringers were investigated (Fig.3 and Fig.8). A piezo-ceramic actuator and four respectively seven ceramic sensor were attached to the structure. Several damage scenarios as well as different environmental conditions were investigated. The test results are presented in Chapter 3.

2 THEORY

2.1 STRUCTURAL MODEL WITH PIEZO-ELECTRIC DEVICES

Assuming the system with n dof behaves linearly, it can be described by the linear differential equation:

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + C_d\dot{x}(t) + Kx(t) = Gu(t) \quad (1)$$

where t denotes continuous time, the vector x represents the displacement, M is the mass matrix, C_d the damping matrix and K the stiffness matrix containing contributions of the structure and the piezo-electric elements, see [3, 4]. The external forces and moments $f(t) = Gu(t)$ can be calculated from the

input matrix G and the input voltage $u(t) = V(t)$. The input voltage $u(t)$ is a zero mean Gaussian white noise signal.

Eq.1 can be rewritten as a first order state space equations where $z^T = (x^T \quad \dot{x}^T)$ is the state vector:

$$A_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & I \\ -M^{-1}K & -M^{-1}C_d \end{bmatrix} \quad B_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ M^{-1}G \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

A_c is a $2n$ by $2n$ state matrix. Eq.1 can thus be written in a more compact form as

$$\dot{z}(t) = A_c z(t) + B_c u(t) \quad (3)$$

Assuming that $u(\tau)$ is constant between sample times and transforming eq.3 from continuous into discrete time yields:

$$z(k+1) = Az(k) + Bu(k) \quad (4)$$

The measurement equation can be written as

$$y(k) = Cz(k) \quad (5)$$

In our case $y(k)$ are the output voltages of the piezo-electric sensors. C is the output matrix. The state space matrix A and the input matrix B in eq.4 are defined as follows:

$$A = e^{A_c \cdot \Delta t} \quad B = \int_0^{\Delta t} e^{A_c \cdot \tau'} d\tau' B_c \quad (6)$$

The output matrix C is unchanged because eq.5 is non-dynamic. If $u(k)$ is stationary white noise with zero mean, the covariance matrix of the input $w(k) = Bu(k)$ can be written as:

$$Q = E((Bu(k))(Bu(k))^T) = \int_{k-\tau}^{(k+1)\tau} e^{A_c \cdot s} \tilde{Q} e^{A_c^T \cdot s} ds \quad (7)$$

with

$$\tilde{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & M^{-1}GQ_u G^T M^{-T} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

and where $E(\cdot)$ denotes the expectation operator. Q_u is defined as $E[u(t)u(t)^T]$.

The modal characteristics can be found in the eigenstructure of A .

$$(A - \delta_i I) \cdot \Psi_i = 0 \quad \text{with} \quad \Delta = \text{diag}\{\delta_1, \delta_2, \dots\} \quad \Psi = [\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \dots] \quad (9)$$

The realization of a stochastic system $[A \ C]$ can be transformed to the realization $[\Delta \ C\Psi]$. The diagonal matrix Δ contains the information of damped natural frequencies and damping rates. The matrix $\Phi = C\Psi$ defines the mode shapes at the sensor points.

The desired damped eigenfrequencies and damping rates are simply the imaginary and real parts of the diagonal matrix Δ , after transformation from the discrete time domain to the continuous time domain using the relation

$$\Delta_c = \ln(\Delta) / \Delta t \quad (10)$$

To interpret the natural frequencies a low pass filter has to be used in order to prevent the frequencies beyond the Nyquist frequency from being folded into a lower frequency [5].

2.2 SUBSPACE-BASED IDENTIFICATION METHOD

To determine the realization, respectively eigenfrequencies, damping coefficients and mode shapes the Subspace-Based Identification Method is used [6, 7]. System realization begins by forming the generalized Hankel matrix composed of the covariances of the sensor outputs

$$R_j \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} E(y(k+j)y^T(k)) \quad (11)$$

of the output $y(k)$ of the state model in eq.5. Let the block-Hankel matrix be:

$$H_{\alpha,\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} R_1 & R_2 & \cdots & R_\beta \\ R_2 & R_3 & \cdots & R_{\beta+1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ R_\alpha & \cdots & \cdots & R_{\alpha+\beta-1} \end{bmatrix} = P_\alpha \cdot Q_\beta \quad (12)$$

The block matrix P_α is the observability matrix and Q_β is the controllability matrix. Choosing the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the state matrix A for the state space model (eq.4) yields the following representation of the observability matrix P_α :

$$P_\alpha = \begin{pmatrix} \Phi \\ \Phi \cdot \Delta \\ \vdots \\ \Phi \cdot \Delta^{\alpha-1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

The diagonal matrix Δ is defined as in eq.10. Φ is the modal matrix whose columns are the eigenvectors. In the case of damage the modes Φ and eigenvalues Δ change, so that also P_α changes.

2.3 THE DAMAGE DETECTION METHOD

A damage indicator can be defined as follows:

$$D_n^2 = \zeta_n^T \hat{\Sigma}^{-1} \zeta_n \quad (14a)$$

$$\zeta_n = \text{vec}(S^T H_{\alpha,\beta,n}) \quad (14b)$$

where ζ_n is the residual and $\hat{\Sigma}$ is an estimate of the residual covariance matrix. $\text{vec}(\dots)$ is the stack operator rearranging the columns of a $m \times n$ matrix in one vector of length $m \cdot n \times 1$. To determine the residual ζ_n and the residual covariance matrix $\hat{\Sigma}$ following steps are necessary:

1. Determine the Hankel-matrix $H_{\alpha,\beta,0}$ of the undamaged structure. The index 0 indicates the undamaged structure.
2. Determine the left kernel space S^T of the Hankel-matrix $H_{\alpha,\beta,0}$, using singular value decomposition (SVD).
3. The product $\text{vec}(S^T H_{\alpha,\beta,n}) = \zeta_n$ defines the residual ζ_n . If the Hankel-matrix is composed of the data of the undamaged structure the residual ζ_n should be close to zero. If damage occurs ζ_n should be significantly different from zero.

4. Determine an estimate of the residual covariance matrix $\hat{\Sigma}$

$$\hat{\Sigma} = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_n \zeta_n \zeta_n^T \quad (15)$$

2.4 DAMAGE DETECTION UNDER CHANGING ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS

The robustness of the damage indicator is an often addressed topic and is very important for the practical implementation. As an example the variation in temperature of an aeroplane under operating conditions can be up to 80 degree Celsius. The variation in temperature causes changes in the stiffness and damping matrix of the differential equation which will end in a modified dynamic behaviour of the structure. The dynamic behaviour of the structure is measured by the piezo-ceramic sensors and processed in the Hankel-matrix. Changes due to variation in temperature will cause a jump of the damage indicator and may result in a false alarm. The goal is to develop a method that makes the damage indicator insensitive concerning variation in temperature. One possibility is to determine the left kernel space as a function of temperature T .

$$\text{vec}(S^T(T)H_{\alpha,\beta}(T)) = \zeta_n \quad (16)$$

This is done experimentally. The matrix $S^T(T)$ is stored in a data base. As the temperature is measured continuously the residual is always computed with the corresponding left kernel space. The results are diagrammed in chapter 3.

3 PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION

The plates were excited by broad band noise with constant spectral density and the voltage response was measured. Figure 2 shows a detailed view of the connection of the piezo-ceramic element with the CFRP plate.

Fig. 2: Connection of piezo-ceramic element and CFRP plate

3.1 CFRP PLATE WITH STRINGERS

In this section the Damage Detection Method is applied to two structures, which are CFRP plates with and without stringers (Fig.3 and Fig.8). The overall size of the plate with stringers is approximately $(490 \times 490 \times 1.9) \text{ mm}$ and its weight is 1.125 kg . The stringers are 36 mm high and 2.5 mm thick. The properties of the UD material are $V_{\text{Fiber}} = 60\%$, $E_{\text{longitudinal}} = 142.6 \text{ GPa}$, $E_{\text{transversal}} = 9.65 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.334$, $\nu_{13} = 0.328$, $\nu_{23} = 0.54$ and $G_{12} = G_{13} = 6.0 \text{ GPa}$. The plate and the stringers consist of 9 plies.

Fig.3: Composite plate with stringers

Fig.4: Delamination after a 5J impact

A piezo-ceramic actuator and four piezo-ceramic sensors were attached to the structure. The plate was excited by broad band noise with constant spectral density within the frequency range of interest. Furthermore, the voltage response of the 4 sensors was measured. After measuring the plate in the undamaged state, a delamination was introduced by an impactor mass with a kinetic energy of about 5 J causing a small damage (Fig.4), which was subsequently increased. Further hints and investigations concerning impact on composite structures are given in [8]. To obtain the size of the delaminations the CFRP plate is inspected by ultrasonic scan. After the first impact the delamination has got a size of about 1 cm^2 , after the second impact about 9 cm^2 . Figure 5 shows the experimental setup for making controlled delaminations. A steel bar (diameter 3.5 cm, with the end rounded (radius 1.75 cm), 20.25 cm long, weight 1.5 kg) is used. To introduce controlled delaminations the steel bar is guided by a tube when falling.

Fig.5: Experimental equipment to introduce defined delaminations

Fig.6: Damage indicator

The energy of the impact is controlled by the selected height. The CFRP plate is always impacted on the flat side. In this example the CFRP plate is supported by small foam cubes at three points. The sampling frequency is 2400Hz . Measurement time is two minutes, which corresponds to about 288000 data samples. The standard deviation of the voltage signal of the actuator is about 0.4 V .

In a first step, a calibration test run, the matrix S^T was obtained by orthogonalization with the Hankel matrix using the SVD. The Hankel matrix was calculated by means of measurement data from the four response channels from the undamaged system. The size of the Hankel matrix is determined by the α and β and the number of the output channels (see eqn. 12). It turned out that $\alpha = \beta \geq 100$ is a suitable choice in order to include the dynamic behavior of the structure. In subsequent runs the matrix S^T was kept constant and the Hankel matrix was recalculated each time using the new sensor output data. As can be seen in Fig. 6 the first 6 measurements correspond to the undamaged plate. The D_n^2 -indicator values are very small. Only the measurement noise causes slight deviation from perfect orthogonality (which corresponds to zero). After these first measurements a significant jump can be seen indicating that the new data do not perfectly correspond with the matrix S^T . This is the point where the first impact on the plate took place. Although the changes of the modal data are very small, it can be seen that the method is very sensitive so that even the damage on the smallest level can be observed. The jump of D_n^2 from undamaged to $5J$ impact is about 400 , the second jump after the second impact is about 650 .

The changes of the PSD due to the delamination are quite small. Fig.7 compares the PSD of undamaged data with data after an impact of about $2 \times 5J$ (dotted line).

Fig.7: Zoom of PSD before and after impact of about $2 \times 5J$

PSD changes occur particularly at higher frequencies. Investigations using the Stochastic Subspace Identification showed that the estimated eigenfrequencies and damping coefficients for measurement no. 1 to 26 do not change significantly.

3.2 INFLUENCE OF VARIATION IN TEMPERATURE TO THE DAMAGE INDICATOR

The overall size of the plate without stringers is approximately $(407 \times 202 \times 2)\text{ mm}$ and its weight is 0.25 kg (Fig.8). It consists of 5 plies, four plies with a specific weight of 0.41 kg/m^2 and one ply with a specific weight of 0.245 kg/m^2 with the same number of fibers lengthwise and across. The properties of the bi-directional material are $V_{Fiber} = (52 - 55)\%$, modulus of elasticity $E = 60\text{ GPa}$ and temperature resistance of about $115\text{-}120^\circ\text{C}$. The damage scenario is a delamination that is introduced by the experimental setup described in the former chapter.

The test runs were performed at $T = 24 \pm 0.5 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature is measured by a *PT100* sensor mounted on the plate surface. The impact energy is about 3J and causes a delamination size of about 0.7 cm^2 determined by ultrasonic scan. Again, the damage is clearly indicated by a jump of the damage indicator (see Fig.9).

Fig.8: CFRP plate in a temperature controlled oven

Fig.9: Damage indicator T=24°C

Afterwards the temperature was raised stepwise up to $T = 80 \pm 0.5 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ and the experiment was repeated. Measurements for the damaged and undamaged structure were taken at each temperature level. Figure 10 shows the result of the damage detection using the left kernel space determined at $T = 24 \pm 0.5 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ again together with the data collected at 80°C level. A jump of the damage indicator can no longer be detected. The influence of the variation in temperature causes a change of structural dynamics [9] that covers the change due to damage. Figure 11 shows the damage indicator using the same Hankel-matrix as before but a different matrix $S^T(T)$ corresponding to the temperature of $T = 80 \pm 0.5 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. Now, the delamination can be clearly detected. This shows that the temperature influence can be compensated if we measure the temperature and the vibration data and recall the matrix $S^T(T)$ for a special temperature level from a data base which can be determined in a “learning phase”.

Fig.10: Damage indicator with S^T_{24}

Fig.11: Damage indicator with S^T_{80}

The question remains if it is possible to detect damage if a data base does only contain matrix S^T in ten degree Celsius steps as used here. Figure 12 shows the damage indicator determined with the matrix S_{24}^T at $T = 24 \pm 0.5^\circ C$ and an environmental temperature that changes from $T = 24 \pm 0.5^\circ C$ to $T = 40 \pm 0.5^\circ C$, so the temperature difference is approximately $\Delta T = 16^\circ C$. The delamination can clearly be detected. The experience of several other experimental investigations with this material is that a database with matrix S^T must be available that contains at least the dynamic characteristics of the structure in $\Delta T = 20^\circ C$ steps.

Fig.12: Damage indicator with S_{24}^T and a temperature change from $T = 24 \pm 0.5^\circ C$ to $T = 40 \pm 0.5^\circ C$

CONCLUSIONS

The detection of delaminations in composite materials is a very challenging task, particularly if the delamination area is small. As delaminations are invisible from the outside, the most commonly used method to detect them is ultrasonic scan, which is a very expensive and time consuming technique. Another possibility is to use the changing vibration characteristics due to damage. Analog to nature a smart structure concept was designed in this paper that is able to perform a self-diagnosis. The structure is equipped with a sensor network and actuation devices. Sensors and actuators are piezo-ceramic elements. As an indicator that an abnormal change has occurred, a residual vector is defined that is based on the actual data and the baseline data of the undamaged system. The disturbance of the orthogonality used for the definition of the residual is very sensitive to the fault. The examples showed that also slight deviations from the nominal behavior could be detected. Another topic investigated here was the robustness of the damage indicator due to variations in temperature by separation of temperature and damage effects. A method is suggested that increases this robustness and experimental results have been presented. We could show that reliable detection of damage is also possible during varying temperatures. Further work should deal with the investigation of other examples and the localization and quantification of the damage.

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